

A study on Innovative ideas used by different genders in Micro-Small Business (MSB) in Coimbatore City

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Abstract

In India Micro-Small Business are developing in recent years. In these circumstances all the youngsters beyond their gender are interested in becoming new flourished entrepreneurs upon the gender they are using new method and innovative ideas to meet this competitive world. Starting a business is not at all a matter but to withstand in the market with their efficiency and effectiveness plays a major role. The main aim of this paper is to find out the what are all the activities focused to improve the MSB, when do the innovative ideas to be cherished inside the MSB and how and where to use the strategies by Micro-Small business while in operation. Both Primary and secondary data are used for study. Paper is empirical in nature as such data were collected with the help of websites. The study emphasized the collection of data from one city, Coimbatore. The sample size is 25.

Keywords : Innovative, strategies, activities, gender, SMB, techniques, withstand.

Introduction

Recently in India the most important creation of conducive and healthy environment for the growth of micro-small business. Since, without gender discrimination both male or female particularly youngsters are very interesting/willing to start a new small scale businesses. It is very important view of economic growth. In fact, Who has the initiative, skill for innovation and who looks for high achievements, with categorized and give the opportunities to do the business. A strong motivational urge being felt by many entrepreneurs. So, during these times, small business must be given the opportunity to continue to be a great source of growth. It backed by guidance, assistance and capital. An entrepreneurial climate must be created to support the entrepreneurial growth strategy. It means the development of the economy has to be interlinked with entrepreneurship, research, innovative ideas, improve business activities and strategies by creating new Micro-Small Business (MSB). Through this effort, the existing business can have a positive impact on the economic growth of a region/country.

Need For The Study

The purpose of this paper is to understand the owner or entrepreneurs mindset with reference to involving of their business. Especially the micro-small business. Further it identifies, Owner's Gender and age frequency. This study explain three part of growing business ideas. First, the activities to be focused to improve the MSB Second, When do the innovative ideas to be cherished in micro-small business and Third, How and Where, we will use the strategies to compete the market. This study is aimed at helping MSB owners have a better understanding the business growth. Its aim also finding what

factors are influence towards the business and owners.

Objective Of The Study

1. What are all the activities to be focused to improve the MSB in different genders.
2. When do the innovative ideas to be cherished MSB in different genders.
3. How and where using the strategies to compete the market.

Hypothesis To Be Tested

1. To find if there is significance relation between factors and the respondents.

Research Methodology

1. Direct investigation method (survey)
2. Area of the study Coimbatore.
3. As a survey method, based on both primary and secondary data used.
4. Sample size is 25. (Random sampling technique)

Research Method

Both primary and secondary data were collected. Sample includes 25 SSBOs. Primary data was collected through questionnaires and interview. Secondary data was from various research papers on the problem, reports, articles and magazines along with the websites.

Statistical Tools Used

1. Simple Percentage analysis
2. Chi-square analysis
3. Hendry Garrett Ranking

2. Literature Review

Zastempowski, Maciej, and Szymon Cyfert (2021)¹ This paper analyses the female gender as a one of the factors that may influence product and process innovativeness of small enterprises. The Sample size 1017. Kujawsko-

pomorskie region in central-northern Poland. The study suggests innovativeness, gender, innovation management capability, and firm characteristics. The study results suggest that the female gender of the entrepreneur has a positive impact on the product and process innovativeness of small enterprises. In the group of small enterprises managed by female entrepreneurs the chances of introducing product innovation are higher by 83.7%, process innovation by 56%, and product and process innovation together by 82.1%.

Pretorius, Marius, Sollie M. Millard, and Maria Elizabeth Kruger² SMME (small, medium and micro-enterprise) development has been identified by the South African government as a priority in creating jobs. This study suggests entrepreneurial education improvement, skills and innovation. This study empirically investigated the perceptions of small venture owners. It was found that number of years management experience, life cycle phase of the venture and race (cultural heritage) but not venture size and gender moderate perception of own creativity. Perception of venture innovativeness was significantly influenced by the life cycle phase of the venture only. Implementation orientation was significantly influenced by the number of years management experience, life cycle phase of the venture, venture size and race but not by gender.

Akulava, Maryia, and Maribel Guerrero (2022)³ Certain principles and prevailing decision-making logics strongly influence entrepreneurial, innovative, and managerial actions. Effectual and causal reasonings provided essential insights into entrepreneurial strategies and innovation outcomes. This study investigates the intersections between causal-effectual reasoning adopted during exploration-exploitation innovation processes, gendered decision-making style and the achievement of radical/incremental innovation outcomes within an organization. A sample size is 407. A study results shows the positive impact of effectual entrepreneurial reasonings on innovation outcomes.

Matricano, Diego (2022)⁴ The aim of this paper is twofold. First, it investigates whether male or female entrepreneurs are better at bringing innovations onto markets by testing the relationship between participation in R&D activities, employment of expert researchers and holding a patent (independent variables) and performance (dependent variable). Second, it investigates the causes of differences, if any. A sample size is 10,676 YICs, The study area is Italy. Finally results confirm the influence of gender only holding for female entrepreneurs and reveal that differences between male and female entrepreneurs depend on random inefficiencies.

Gligor, David, Ivan Russo, and Michael J.

Maloni (2022)⁵ Extant studies of the drivers of logistics innovation have focused on firm-level attributes, largely neglecting micro-level attributes associated with individual logistics professionals engaged in the innovation process as well as the environments in which they work. This includes gender differences. Consequently, we draw on organizational management research and complexity theory to evaluate gender-specific combinations of logistics innovation antecedents, including individual-level attributes such as self-efficacy, willingness to change, and creativity, as well as job-level attributes such as job satisfaction, training, and job complexity. This paper findings offer important insights into how firms can orchestrate their logistics innovation teams to meet rapidly changing customer needs.

3. Overview Of The Study

1 The activities to be focused to improve the MSB in different gender are,

Every business activities around Technical, Commercial, Financial, Security, Accounting and Managerial functions. Apart from these, to stimulate way, without gender partiality, an entrepreneur to be focused to improve their skill and knowledge to do the micro-small business. First of all every entrepreneur/owner must know their skill, knowledge, leadership quality, ability and spirit. The study highlighted the entrepreneur/owner activities as follows:

1. **Entrepreneurial spirit:** A leader senses, targets and accomplishes his goal and self-efficacy is central to the heart of the entrepreneurial spirit. People who showcase high levels of entrepreneurial spirit tend to have high self-efficacy when it comes to entrepreneurial ventures – this self-starter mentality can pay dividends when it comes to overcoming challenges and tackling issues head-on and need to be steadfastly surmounted through self-belief, conviction and a never-say-die attitude.
2. **Innovation:** This quality makes a team deliver successfully overtime is innovation. An Entrepreneur/owner realises that the timeless adage 'Don't react to the change. Be the change' holds true throughout the life of a business, to create a space and place for connection and collaboration, to map the ethnography of employees and customers and start small while seeking the scale of a business.
3. **Simplicity:** It wins everytime. That means the ideas of the owner will reach and be understood by each member of a business. The virtue of simplicity, coupled with assertiveness, determines the effectiveness of an entrepreneur/owner.
4. **Quality:** An entrepreneur have to maintaining

their quality at work as an infallible way of ensuring a business success. Demanding perfection while realising each person's limitations is the essence of good successful ownership/ entrepreneurship.

5. **Knowledge:** Knowledge helps develop perspective. It also opens up the mind and removes biases and it is this that helps owner to see the big picture and develop an agenda that is aligned not only to the present but also future.
6. **Risks:** Every business owners always take risks. There is no single leader style that works everywhere. A successful owner adapts their style to the business and uses it for the business and workers benefit. A good owner/ entrepreneur, is one who understands the business organisation and its workers, creates goals accordingly and executes them effectively.

Empowerment of people: 'Create a Reality Where You Can Think Big, Act Big' an entrepreneur to encourage their people to participate in decision – making and is open to their ideas and suggestions.

Decision-making: Decisiveness is one of the key traits an entrepreneur must possess. Indecision is the biggest risk in business and a owner cannot afford to be fickle-minded.

Ethics: Entrepreneurship is built on trust. An entrepreneur need to ensure that their conduct inspires the confidence to make inside people of the business, they lead. It must consistently espouse and act upon their values, standards and principles in their public as well as private lives.

Commonsense: Success as a owner/entrepreneur, therefore, does not come from specialised training or education. It comes from commonsense and from the ability to learn from others. Example of successful leadership are visible in plenty all around us – in different situations, in different social groups, as also in different organisations. The trick is to comprehend the behavioural patterns of these people that lead them to be exceptionally brilliant as a ownership.

Exemplification: Credibility comes from walking the talk. Stepping front to take risks simply and leading the charge.

Decisiveness: An entrepreneur/owner listen to all but do what they is best for their business.

A business owner/ entrepreneur must rely on their intuition while making key decisions.

Trusting by delegation: It must be liberal in appreciating such extra effort – this goes a long way in acting as a morale-booster for the team-members and, in turn, helps increase the productivity and efficiency of the organisation structure.

The ability to think differently: For example, who able to ask, 'what can I get out of my business team members?' Instead of a 'what does my business

team want from me?' to realise this vision. The key, therefore, is to think differently and be innovative in one's approach to handling in an organisation.

Faith: It display unwavering faith in their dreams and remain focused with a strong to pursue dreams. It give due credit for success to their co-workers while taking responsibility for failures. A owner of a business are also those who remain humble in their disposition because humility allows them to learn from subordinates who may have a few good lessons to teach.

Communication: Through communicate to inform, convince, unite, motivate and direct their flock. The power to inform and persuade is critical to winning the hearts and minds of employees- something that is essential to leading organisations effectively.

2 The innovative ideas to be cherished MSB in different genders are,

Gender equality is a fundamental human right. Yet despite progress, a innovative ideas offering a particular circumstances in the workplace, market place and community. A leadership in business a key components of every small business. In this point, man or women called as a business term Owner or Entrepreneur. A good entrepreneur evaluates a new situation in their environment and directs the making of such adjustment ideas in the economy of the business as deems necessary. When do the innovative ideas to be cherished in micro-small business as follows.

Perceiving the need and analysing own-self in relation to life goals..

Scanning the environment opportunities.

1. Identification of place, product/project and profit maximisation.
2. Conducting market survey.
3. Identification of technology advancement, plant and equipment.
4. Preparation of report business plan.
5. Arranging initial capital or finance
6. Arranging infrastructure and utilities.
7. Making organisation structure.
8. Project or business implementation.
9. Marketing and sales management
10. Advance knowledge to using social media strategies.
11. Management of business and excusion of process.
12. The Unexpected failure and unexpected external event.
13. Innovative ideas were included in this part of creativity, administrative part, to set a objectives, to maintain business secrecy, emotional stability, human relationship, failure of guidance, threatening shadow of changing technology and communication etc.,

3 The strategies to compete the market

At present, we want to know about the

strategies to compete the market. If small business owner with little experience in online marketing, creating a strategy to boost online presence may feel overwhelming. In this point, this study help to build and optimize small business marketing strategy using market setting up to attract new entrepreneurs and ultimately grow the small business. How and Where, we will use the strategies to compete the market as follows:

Understanding the public interest.

1. To Emphasize the value of a business promises to deliver to customers should they choose to buy their product.
2. Making clean Environment
3. Create marketing design
4. Achiving goal & objective
5. Collecting of creating a form of capital.
6. Understand the power of existing customers.
7. Improve their act of raising in rank or position.

8. Strategy were used to setup an online presence for the business.
9. How to attract prospects.
10. Smart strategy to use in social media
11. At the time of customer service.
12. The stratagies are using in email marketing.
13. To manage the smooth relationship with customer and to learn word of mouth as promotionof distribution channels (the strategy to create chains of marketing)
14. To determine the brand’s identity, logo, buyer intention and business assets.
15. The strategy use to marketing experiments like Photos, video content and working models.
16. To encourage happy customers, to offer a free webinar Expo And Offer Coupons In News Letter.

Interpretation, Analsis and Findings:

1. Respondents Gender and Age Frequency in Simple Percentage analysis.

Table 1

Sex Frequency	Respondents	Percentage
Male	12	48%
Female	13	52%
Total	25	100%
Different Age group	Respondents	Percentage
20-30 years	10	40%
31-40 years	8	32%
41-50 years	3	12%
51-60 years	2	8%
Above 60 years	2	8%
Total	25	100%

From total 25 respondents in sex frequency indicated 12% of male respondent were willing to start a business. 13% of female respondent were willing to start a business. Thus, 15% majority is female respondent. From total 25 respondents in different2age group indicated 40% of 20-30 years

respondent. 32% of 31-40 years respondent. 12% Of 41-50 years respondent. 8% of 51-60 years respondent. 8% of above 60 years. Thus, the majority is 20-30 years age group of people’s were intrested to startinga small business.

When do the innovative ideas to be focused to improve the business in Chi-square analyses.Table 1

Respondents / Factors	Strongly Agreed Respondents	Agreed Respondents	Not Agreed Respondents	Total Respondents
Initial Capital	40	6	7	53
Business Plan	30	12	8	50
Organisation Structure	32	20	4	56
Market Survey	35	25	3	63
Technology	42	14	7	63
Execution techniques	45	12	8	65
	224	89	37	350

Calculation of Chi-square **(Observation Value – Expected Value)²Expected Value**
(Chi-square) Calculated Value

Sl.No	OV	EX.V	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	40	33.92	6.08	36.97	1.09
2	6	13.48	-7.48	55.91	4.15
3	7	5.60	1.40	1.95	0.35
4	30	32.00	-2.00	4.00	0.13
5	12	12.71	-0.71	0.51	0.04
6	8	5.29	2.71	7.37	1.39
7	32	35.84	-3.84	14.75	0.41
8	20	14.24	5.76	33.18	2.33
9	4	5.92	-1.92	3.69	0.62
10	35	40.32	-5.32	28.30	0.70
11	25	16.02	8.98	80.64	5.03
12	3	6.66	-3.66	13.40	2.01
13	42	40.32	1.68	2.82	0.07
14	14	16.02	-2.02	4.08	0.25
15	7	6.66	0.34	0.12	0.02
16	45	41.60	3.40	11.56	0.28
17	12	16.53	-4.53	20.51	1.24
18	8	6.87	1.13	1.27	0.19
Total					20.30

Null Hypothesis: There is no significance relation between factors and the respondents. Alternative Hypothesis : There is significance relation between factors and the respondents.

Degrees of Freedom = (Columns – 1) (Rows – 1)
 = (3-1) (6-1), 2 x 5 = 10

Alternative Hypothesis : There is significance relation between factors and the respondents.

4. In Which and where the strategies used by order.

Significance level (alpha) = 0.05. X^2 (Tabular =18.31; Calculated X^2 = 20.30)
 X^2 Calculated > X^2 Tabular.
 Therefore, we reject null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis.

Rank	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	1	1	3	1	0	3	1	15
2	0	2	3	1	0	2	14	3
3	3	3	2	0	1	12	2	2
4	1	2	8	4	3	3	3	1
5	7	4	4	3	1	2	2	2
6	0	6	1	3	11	2	1	1
7	3	3	2	10	4	1	1	1
8	10	4	2	3	5	0	1	0

F1 = Making Clean Environment, **F2** = Improving Position, **F3** = Online Marketing, **F4** = Marketing structure, **F5** = Brand identify, **F6** = Customer Service, **F7** = Understand the power of Ex-Coustomer **F8** = Achieving Goal & Objectives

N_j = Total rank given by 25 respondents = 8

Percent position = $100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$
 R_{ij} = 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th ranks

Table 3. Garret value is found for the percent position

Garret value

Rank	100(Rij-0.5)	Percent position
1	100(1-0.5)/8	6.25
2	100(2-0.5)/8	18.75
3	100(3-0.5)/8	31.25
4	100(4-0.5)/8	43.75
5	100(5-0.5)/8	56.25
6	100(6-0.5)/8	68.75
7	100(7-0.5)/8	81.25
8	100(8-0.5)/8	93.75

Rank	Percent position Value	Garret value
1	6.25	80
2	18.75	67
3	31.25	59
4	43.75	53
5	56.25	46
6	68.75	40
7	81.25	32
8	93.75	20

For each rank, garret value is multiplied by given value and all the calculated values are totalled row wise.

Table 4. Garret score total

Factor/ Rank	1*80	2*67	3*59	4*53	5*46	6*40	7*32	8*20	total
F1	80	0	177	53	322	0	96	200	928
F2	80	134	177	106	184	240	96	80	1097
F3	240	201	118	424	184	40	64	40	1311
F4	80	67	0	212	138	120	320	60	997
F5	0	0	59	159	46	440	128	100	932
F6	240	134	708	159	92	80	32	0	1445
F7	80	938	118	159	92	40	32	20	1479
F8	1200	201	118	53	92	40	32	0	1736

The total score is divided by number of respondents to calculate average score, then rank the highest average score as I and the least average score with rank VIII.

Table 5. Garret Rank

Factors	Total	Average Score	Rank
F1- Making Clean Environment	928	37.12	VIII
F2- Improving Position	1097	43.88	V
F3- Online Marketing	1311	52.44	IV
F4- Marketing structure	997	39.88	VI
F5- Brand Identify	932	37.28	VII
F6- Customer Service	1445	57.80	III
F7- Understanding the power of Existing Customer	1479	59.16	II
F8- Achieving Goal & Objectives	1736	69.44	I

From the above table, it is identified that the variable, F8 – Achieving goal & objectives ranks first, the variable, F7 – Understanding the power of existing customer ranks second, the variable F6 – Customer service ranks third, the variable F3 – Online

Marketing ranks fourth, the variable F2 – Improving position ranks fifth, the variable F4 – Marketing structure ranks sixth, the variable F5- Brand identify ranks seventh, the variable F1 – Making clean environment ranks eighth.

5. The activities to be focused to improve the business:

Activities	Respondents	Percentage
Innovation	8	32%
Quality	4	16%
Risks	6	24%
Decision making	4	16%
Business Ethics	3	12%
Total	25	100

From total 25 respondents in different activities to be focused to improving the small business. 32% of business owners are focusing innovation activities. 16% of respondent are focusing quality activities. 24% of respondent are focusing Risk activities. 16% of respondent are focusing Decision making activities. 12% are focusing Business Ethics activities.

Therefore, The majority respondents are focusing Innovation Activities.

Summary Of Findings, Suggestions And Conclusion

Findings:

1. The majority is 20-30 years age group of people's were interested to starting a small business.
2. The majority is 20-30 years age group of people's were interested to starting a small business.
3. There is significance relation between factors and the respondents.
4. The majority respondents are focusing Innovation Activities.

Suggestions:

1. Awareness programmed may be conducted entire age group of the people, particularly youth population is highest level at present. Regarding the business activities, innovative ideas and strategies.
2. Training should be provided to the existing MSB owners.
3. The government will provide loan facilities, incentives and to encourage to the Micro-Small level Business.
4. The government will support the repayment of loan amount and to check the owners
5. mind. Owner can affect any stress or any depression mindset.

Conclusion:

The Micro-Small Business(MSB) has vital role at present upward fragment of the livestock zone. In India owing to a number of positive reasons and the MSB contributing to nation wide GDP. Looking by the side of present information proposed by MSB owners, Coimbatore City. MSB be able to be focus for more people. The researcher requested the suggestion is made on the basis of this study. The government take considerations of improving the MSB. The business owners accept

their responsibility with all your heart and perform the business in well manner that fulfilled the human race.

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